

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Deliverable D3.2

Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills
for Democratic Participation

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Glossary

Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
Critical Literacies Framework	The Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
D	Deliverable
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
O	Objective
PAR	Participatory Action Research
P	Phase
RFDCDC	The Council of Europe Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and examines the current state of democracy in learning environments across Europe, generating a robust evidence base for the design of a participatory democratic curriculum. Critical ChangeLab develops a model for democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. At the Critical ChangeLabs, diverse actors from formal and non-formal education and civic organizations work together with youth to rethink European democracy and envision futures that are justice-oriented.

This deliverable presents the revised version of the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy and introduces its key components: (i) Critical Literacies Framework, (ii) Competency Framework, (iii) Pedagogical Process, (iv) Methodological Repertoire, and (v) Assessment. This revised version of the Critical ChangeLab Model builds on D3.1 by refining the critical literacies framework, clarifying the competency structure, and strengthening the pedagogical process based on insights from the participatory action research cycles and process evaluation findings.

1 Introduction

1.1 About Critical ChangeLab

Critical ChangeLab (Democracy Meets Arts: Critical Change Labs for Building Democratic Cultures through Creative and Narrative Practices) is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project addressing democratic erosion trends by strengthening youth participation in society. The project is carried out by 10 partner institutions and embraces a transdisciplinary approach combining expertise from Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, as well as Science and Technology.

Specifically, the Critical ChangeLab project develops a model of democratic pedagogy using creative and narrative practices to foster youth's active democratic citizenship at a time when polarisation and dwindling trust in democracy are spreading across Europe. The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy fosters learners' transformative agency and strengthens democratic processes in education through collaborations across formal and non-formal education and local actors around global/local challenges relevant for youth. The Model promotes creative and narrative practices to explore the historical roots of local and EU-wide challenges, understanding the value-systems and worldviews underlying distinct types of relations (human-human, human-nature, human-technology). This principle was operationalised in the Critical ChangeLabs by enabling young participants to define the issues addressed, shape the learning process, and decide on forms of action. At the Labs, young people are introduced to approaches such as theatre of the oppressed, transmedia storytelling, as well as speculative and critical design to rethink European democracy and envision alternative democracy futures.

Throughout its duration, the Critical ChangeLab project examines the current state of democracy within education institutions developing instruments such as the Democracy Health Questionnaire and Index, as well as conducting case studies to identify youth's perspectives on everyday democracy. As part of the project, a scalable and tailorable model of democratic pedagogy in formal and non-formal learning environments is designed. The Critical ChangeLab Model is co-created and implemented with youth and stakeholders and evaluated to provide recommendations for policy and practice. Strategies to sustain the model and its outcomes over time are also produced.

The Critical ChangeLab project uses a mixed-method research design that combines quantitative and in-depth qualitative research on democracy and youth with participatory action

research (PAR) cycles, with findings from each strand directly informing the iterative development and refinement of the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy. Together, these findings generate a robust evidence base to support democratic curriculum development using participatory, creative, and critical approaches.

1.2 Context of the deliverable within WP3 - Evaluate

This deliverable (D3.2) has been developed in the context of WP3, led by UB, and informed by the process evaluation (T3.1). In particular, insights from T3.1 highlighted strengths and tensions in implementation that directly informed revisions to the initial version of the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy¹. D3.2 addresses the Critical ChangeLab objective of designing a democratic pedagogy model that integrates creative and narrative practices with learners and civic education stakeholders.

1.3 Relationship of the deliverable to other work packages

This deliverable (D3.2) responds to Critical ChangeLab project objectives:

- O2: Design a scalable and tailorable model – Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy.
- O3: Co-create and implement the Critical ChangeLab Model in collaboration with stakeholders.
- O5: Sustain the Critical ChangeLab activities beyond the Critical ChangeLab project lifespan.

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy (D3.2) is strongly linked to other WP deliverables such as D1.4 Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit (WP1) and D2.3 Critical ChangeLab Educator’s Handbook (WP2). While D1.4 provided the basis to guide implementation during the Participatory Action Research (PAR) cycles, D2.3 extends and adapts the Critical ChangeLab approach to guide educational practice. The Critical ChangeLab Model is informed by robust empirical evidence collected as part of WP1, WP2 and analysed in WP3 tasks.

The process evaluation conducted under T3.1 and presented in D3.1 Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice² has played a central role in refining the Critical ChangeLab Model by systematically examining how the initial model functioned in practice during PAR cycles 2 and 3. Through observation, reflective documentation, and dialogue with facilitators and

¹ Initial version of the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy was presented in D1.4 Critical ChangeLab Model: Framework and Toolkit. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/14259812>

² D3.1 Critical ChangeLab process and recommendations for practice is available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab/records>

participants, the process evaluation identified strengths in fostering youth engagement and democratic participation, as well as tensions related to facilitation, sequencing of activities, and the operationalisation of key concepts. These insights informed targeted revisions to the Model, leading to clearer articulation of its pedagogical phases, strengthened alignment between conceptual frameworks and practice, and enhanced guidance for educators and stakeholders implementing the Labs.

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy plays a key role in the dissemination activities related to sustainability carried out in WP4. Through these actions, the Model is introduced to professional communities in youth work and education as a flexible resource that can support their ongoing efforts in democracy and citizenship education. In addition, the Model is closely aligned with the recommendations presented in the Critical ChangeLab policy briefs, offering a concrete and operationalisable resource to guide practice.

Table 1 summarises how specific tasks from WP1, WP2, and WP3 contributed to the development process and informed the updated version of the Model presented in this deliverable. Table 1 also shows how D3.2 links to the WP4 tasks related to sustainability by supporting empowerment actions and helping to put the recommendations for practice into action.

Table 1. Connection between WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4 tasks and D3.2

WP	Task	Ways in which D3.2 builds on the task
1	Task 1.3 Development of a conceptual and methodological framework for supporting critical democracy education through creative and narrative practices	First version of the Model that has been iterated in D3.2 after its implementation in the PAR cycles.
1	Task 1.4 PAR cycle 1	The insights and learnings from each PAR cycle, where the initial version of the Model was implemented, formed an integral part of the co-creation approach.
2	Task 2.2 PAR Cycle 2: implementation of the first iteration of the Critical ChangeLabs	The insights and learnings from each PAR cycle, where the initial version of the Model was implemented, formed an integral part of the co-creation approach.
2	Task 2.3 PAR Cycle 3, implementation of the second iteration of the Critical ChangeLabs	The insights and learnings from each PAR cycle, where the initial version of the Model

		was implemented, formed an integral part of the co-creation approach.
2	Task 2.4 Development of the Critical ChangeLab Educator’s Handbook	The Critical ChangeLab Educator’s Handbook (D2.4) was developed drawing on insights from the PAR cycles and closely aligned with the revised version of the Model.
3	Task 3.1. Process evaluation	The evaluation of the Critical ChangeLab process during PAR 2 and PAR 3 provided the empirical basis for revising the initial version of the Model.
4	T4.3 Community empowerment activities for a sustained take up of methods	The Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy is introduced in the MOOC developed as part of T4.3 targeting youth workers and educators. The Model is shared and discussed as part of teacher training and professional development actions.
4	T4.5 Definition of implications for policy	The Critical ChangeLab Model responds to various recommendations and calls for action presented in policy briefs (D4.5 Policy brief 2 and D4.6 Policy recommendations on citizenship education for sustainable European democracy).

2 Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy

2.1 Theoretical Influences

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy builds on Dewey’s view that democracy is more than a form of government; it is “primarily a form of associated living, of conjoint communicated experience” (Dewey, 1916, p.91). From this perspective, democracy education is understood as a collective and shared process, where learning becomes a co-construction of knowledge and students and teachers engage as relatively equal participants (Hopkins, 2018). Drawing on the educational philosophies of Paulo Freire, bell hooks, and Henry Giroux, the model emphasizes participatory approaches that empower youth to creatively address democratic challenges. In particular, hooks argues that democracy is not merely about formal institutions but

about transforming social relations to eliminate domination—an idea that underscores the role of education as a space for cultivating critical consciousness and fostering democratic practices in everyday life (hooks, 1994). Building on this, the Critical ChangeLab approach considers young people not as future citizens but as citizens with political agency in the present (Sanchini et al., 2019), holding rights and responsibilities within cosmopolitan and increasingly globalized societies (Osler & Starkey, 2003). A key assumption is that participatory democracy is learned through participation (Biesta, 2007), which means creating educational environments where youth actively engage in decision-making, dialogue, and collaborative problem-solving as part of their democratic learning experience.

The Critical ChangeLab Model is inspired by a research assisted intervention method called the Change Laboratory, adaptations of which have been used in various settings including schools, hospitals, postal services, libraries and entrepreneurship education (Engeström et al., 2023; Kajamaa, 2011; Haapasaari et al., 2016; Engeström et al., 2013; Morselli et al., 2014). Drawing from cultural-historical activity theory (Vygotsky, 197; Leont'ev, 1978) and the theory of expansive learning, the Change Laboratory method aims to structure collaborative design efforts by helping participants to identify, analyse and resolve systemic contradictions and conceptualize the object of collective activity (Kajamaa & Hyrkkö, 2022). At the heart of expansive learning is the idea of learning something that is not yet there (Engeström, 2015), which further emphasises its participatory nature allowing the participants to make use of their own voices, knowledge and experiences in the collective design process and taking ownership of the process (Kajamaa & Hyrkkö, 2022).

Overcoming systemic contradictions requires people involved in the activity to take transformative action. This kind of agency means breaking away from the usual way of doing things and taking the initiative to change it (Virkkunen, 2006). Transformative agency is also linked to what Kajamaa and Kumpulainen (2019) describe as a “transformative activist stance,” where people work to improve existing practices for personal or collective reasons. In doing so, they often develop their own identity and learn along the way.

Taken together, these theoretical traditions frame democratic pedagogy as a participatory, relational, and transformative endeavour. Dewey provides the foundation for understanding learning as a social and collective process, while Freire, hooks, and Giroux highlight the role of education in developing critical consciousness and addressing inequitable power relations. Cultural-historical activity theory and expansive learning complement these perspectives by offering a process-oriented lens on how contradictions, experimentation, and collective action can drive the transformation of practices. In synthesising these strands, the Critical ChangeLab

Model foregrounds learning through participation, values young people's lived experiences as legitimate knowledge sources, and conceives democratic education as an ongoing collective project oriented toward social change. The following sections elaborate on the Critical ChangeLab Model's approach, design process, and main elements.

2.2 Approach

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy supports the Council of Europe's mission to strengthen democracy by fostering a culture of democratic practices (Council of Europe, 2016). The model is built around three core principles: (i) youth-centeredness, (ii) participation with an emphasis on everyday democracy, and (iii) an orientation toward change. These principles reflect the Critical ChangeLab approach to education for democracy, which views learning environments as spaces for practicing everyday democracy, understands democracy in education as an attitude that values youth agency, and incorporates knowledge democracy—embracing epistemological pluralism—as part of lived democratic experiences. In practice, epistemological pluralism is enacted by deliberately valuing experiential, creative, and community-based knowledges alongside academic perspectives, and by designing activities that enable these forms of knowledge to interact and inform collective inquiry and decision-making.

Informed by an understanding of democracy as a culture, the Critical ChangeLab Model advances 21st-century learning for youth (ages 11–18) by fostering core skills needed to participate effectively, responsibly, and critically in democratic societies. It also contributes to the European Democracy Shield and the EU Strategy for Civil Society by boosting societal resilience and citizens' engagement³. The ChangeLab Model recognizes the importance of skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and global/intercultural competence (see Griffin et al., 2012), linking them with the Council of Europe Reference Framework knowledge, skills and values for building democratic cultures by elaborating on four core competences: critical understanding of the world, imagination and creativity, transformative agency, and democratic disposition—essential for addressing today's democratic challenges.

A central aspect of the Critical ChangeLab is the collaboration and active involvement of civil society actors in young people's democracy education. The Model is deeply rooted in the participatory tradition of democracy and aims to facilitate learning experiences in which key actors for democracy education—youth, formal and non-formal educators, and civil society

³ The press release on European Democracy Shield and EU Strategy for Civil Society is available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_2660

organizations such as associations, non-governmental agencies, and small and medium enterprises—meet and collaborate. In the Critical ChangeLabs, young people, educators, and civil society actors are regarded as experts in identifying their own needs and aspirations for engaging in associated living with others (Dewey, 1916).

A Critical ChangeLab is an educational format for democracy where young people collaborate to identify, question, and examine issues that create tensions in their everyday lives, and to envision alternatives for more desirable futures. These Labs focus on topics that are relevant to the participants and their local context. Within the Labs, youth work alongside stakeholders from education and civil society to explore these issues collectively. The orientation toward change is understood broadly—from shifting how democratic issues in daily life are perceived and understood to taking concrete actions within youth’s own environments. In both cases, change involves reimagining Western democracies’ anthropocentric worldviews and fostering relationships of care with other humans, the environment, and other sentient beings. It also includes recognizing the mediating role of tools and technologies and rethinking how they can contribute to building desirable futures as part of the transformative processes initiated in Critical ChangeLabs. At the Labs, transformation and change may take the form of shifts in understanding, altered relationships, or small-scale actions within participants’ everyday contexts, rather than only large-scale or institutional transformations. These changes are understood as meaningful when they reshape how young people perceive democratic issues, relate to others, and exercise agency within the social, educational, and civic environments they inhabit.

The Critical ChangeLab Model is rooted in democracy and citizenship education and designed with flexibility to suit both formal and non-formal contexts. It remains open and adaptable to local conditions, settings, participants, and stakeholders. Minimum requirements include a project-based approach and dedicated time for reflection. The Model does not prescribe formats or tools, allowing Labs to run face-to-face, online, or in hybrid form. However, in-person sessions are strongly recommended, especially for sustained engagement with young people.

2.3 Design process

The Critical ChangeLab Model of Democratic Pedagogy is a flexible framework designed for diverse learning environments. It emerged through a co-creation process involving multiple stakeholders in a series of Participatory Action Research (PAR) cycles. In this context, stakeholders include: (i) education and civil society organizations partnering to run Critical ChangeLabs, (ii)

educators, facilitators, and civil society actors engaged in Lab activities, and (iii) young people participating in the Labs.

The adoption of a co-creation approach is grounded on research showing its value in fostering engagement, collective intelligence, and creativity (Durall et al., 2019; Frow et al., 2015; Sanders & Stappers, 2008). From these perspectives, co-creation is an overarching concept realized through co-design activities—specific instances where stakeholders collaboratively explore, plan, and learn about issues (Mattelmäki & Visser, 2011). Both co-creation and co-design approaches emphasize process and transformation (Manzini, 2014; Voorberg et al., 2015).

In the Critical ChangeLabs, co-creation is enacted through the active involvement of young people. From the start, the Labs are designed to offer youth meaningful opportunities to identify the issues that matter to them and to take the lead in shaping responses to those issues. This hands-on role cultivates a strong sense of ownership over both the challenges they surface and the alternatives they envision. Such ownership is essential for fostering meaningful and lasting change in practice (Mäntylä & Visser, 2011; Voorberg et al., 2015; Ramirez, 2008; Roschelle et al., 2006).

At the same time, the co-creation process involves navigating differing expectations, power relations, and institutional constraints among stakeholders—notably between youth participants, educators, and organizational partners. Addressing these tensions required continuous reflection and adaptation of facilitation strategies. These adjustments, in turn, informed the iterative development of the model and strengthened its core emphasis on shared ownership and democratic decision-making.

Critical ChangeLabs are designed as collaborative spaces, involving not only the young people who take part in the activities but also designers, facilitators, and stakeholders from both formal and non-formal education organisations⁴. The Lab itself is the result of a co-design process that brings these different actors together. Research on participatory and co-design approaches shows that such collaboration supports sustainability by encouraging adoption and new ways of working (Durall et al., 2019; Treasure-Jones & Joynes, 2018) and helps foster engagement, teamwork, and empowerment (Durall et al., 2019; Kwon et al., 2014; Matuk et al., 2016).

⁴ See Critical ChangeLab D1.4 for the Critical ChangeLab co-design toolkit. Available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14259812>

2.4 Elements

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy is built around five key components: (i) conceptual and (ii) competency frameworks, (iii) a defined pedagogical process, (iv) diverse methodological repertoire, and (v) a participatory approach to assessment. These components are intended to function as an integrated system, with each element reinforcing and informing the others throughout the Critical ChangeLab process. The conceptual and competency frameworks provide orientation, the pedagogical process structures learning over time, the methodological repertoire enables diverse forms of engagement, and participatory assessment supports reflection and iteration across all stages. Next, each of the components is briefly introduced:

Critical ChangeLab conceptual framework: The conceptual framework guiding the Critical ChangeLab process and the selection of methods is referred to as the Critical Literacies Framework. This framework draws on literature related to criticality, relationality, and futures (see Section 3 for a detailed elaboration). It serves as a compass for Critical ChangeLab designers, helping them identify key aspects to emphasize during Lab sessions.

Critical ChangeLab competency framework: Building on the Council of Europe's Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC), Critical ChangeLab identifies four key competences to guide education for democracy: (i) critical understanding of the world, (ii) imagination and creativity, (iii) transformative agency, and (iv) democratic disposition. These competences were co-defined with stakeholders throughout the PAR cycles to support reflection and assessment of the Labs. Section 4 provides a detailed description of these competences.

Critical ChangeLab pedagogical process: Critical ChangeLabs build on project- and inquiry-based learning. Learning is conceived as a process where youth begin by questioning everyday relations and identifying tensions tied to democratic values. They then (i) collectively define and analyse the topic, (ii) imagine alternative futures and broaden democratic understandings, and (iii) materialise ideas in practice. Reflection is embedded throughout, culminating in a final session where participants review their experiences. Further details are provided in Section 5.

Critical ChangeLab methodological repertoire: The methods used at the Critical ChangeLabs stem from various traditions such as arts and design, futures, relational pedagogy, participatory research and community engagement. At the Labs, various methods might be combined to foster participants' collaboration, critical thinking and creativity to tackle current democracy challenges. Further elaboration on the Critical ChangeLab methods is provided in section 6.

Participatory assessment: The Critical ChangeLab Model views assessment as a continuous, democratic, and dialogic process embedded throughout the learning cycle rather than as a separate, summative event. It emphasizes participation, where learners co-create criteria, provide feedback, and share responsibility, prioritizing formative assessment over grades or rankings. Further elaboration is provided in section 7.

3 Critical Literacies Framework

The Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework (hereafter referred to as the Critical Literacies Framework) serves as a robust instrument for guiding the planning and facilitation of Critical Change Labs, ensuring that participants undergo a comprehensive development of critical literacies. Rooted in the seminal work of Paulo Freire (1970), critical literacy is fundamentally concerned with fostering a critical consciousness, or *conscientização*, which empowers individuals to identify and challenge prevailing power dynamics and systems of oppression within society. In the contemporary context, being critically literate extends beyond conventional textual comprehension, encompassing various forms of media such as video, online content, music, and data-driven technologies like Artificial Intelligence, as well as more traditional texts. To become critically literate means that students will have mastered the ability to read and critique messages from a wide variety of sources in order to better understand whose knowledge is being privileged (Van Sluys, Lewison and Flint., 2006), and to begin to understand and foster the capacity to be agents of change against social injustices (Freire & Macedo, 1987; Shor, 1999).

The Critical Literacies Framework was constructed following scoping and systematic literature reviews of existing critical literacy frameworks for youth in formal and non-formal education settings, including the Four Resources Model (Luke and Freebody, 1997), the Four Dimensions of Critical Literacy (FCDL) model (Lewison, Flint and Van Sluys, 2002), the Five Steps Framework (Janks, 2014), among other established frameworks and suggested dimensions. The applied Critical Literacies Framework also integrates aspects from relational literature from the fields of ethics (De La Bellacasa, 2012; Metz & Miller, 2016) pedagogy (Biesta et al., 2004; Hickey & Riddle, 2022), sustainability (West et al., 2020), as well as from other fields influenced by a relational turn such as social sciences (Powell & Dépelteau, 2013; Selg, 2016), design (Nielsen & Bjerck, 2022) and Human-Computer Interaction (Filimowicz & Tzankova, 2018). Other relevant sources of inspiration stem from posthumanism (see Hultman & Lenz Taguchi, 2010; Sheridan et al., 2020; Zapata et al. 2018). Adding to the prior influences, pedagogical frameworks focused on futures literacy (see Häggström & Schmidt, 2021; Mangnus et al., 2021) are also particularly relevant to the goals of the Critical ChangeLab Model.

The Critical Literacies Framework comprises four key dimensions and one transversal dimension. Engagement with all five dimensions is required to foster and develop critical literacies in students meaningfully. While the framework is structured in a semi-linear progression, commencing with 'Understanding' and culminating in 'Activating Change', the developmental journey of critical literacies inherently entails nonlinear trajectories. Educators and participants alike may traverse

dimensions non sequentially or concurrently engage with multiple dimensions, reflecting the dynamic and multifaceted nature of critical literacy development.

The dimensions of the Framework are as follows (see also figure 1 for a visual summary):

- Understanding
- Identifying
- Deconstructing
- Activating change
- Processes of becoming

The Framework dimensions were selected to ensure that critical literacy development moves from understanding and analysis toward action and sustained reflection, rather than remaining at the level of critique alone. Together, they structure a learning trajectory that supports participants in building foundational knowledge, critically examining power relations and assumptions, and actively engaging in change-making practices. The inclusion of a transversal dimension further ensures that reflection on learning processes and positionality is sustained beyond individual activities, supporting longer-term development of critical literacies.

3.1 Understanding

The base level of comprehension and contextual knowledge needed before the journey of developing critical literacies can begin. This includes (i) meanings of critical literacy, (ii) democratic practices and citizenship, and (iii) basic knowledge of the subject or topic that is the focus of the Critical ChangeLab.

3.2 Identifying

The second dimension is about recognising issues that are creating conflict and contradictions in democratic systems. This includes examining the embodied nature of conflicts, their situated and interrelated character, and the historical dimension or trajectory that has led to a particular situation.

3.3 Deconstructing

The third dimension involves interrogating the cultural construction of the “source” (e.g. text, concept, object), its social and political context, and societal transformation. This includes three different aspects:

(a) Disrupting the commonplace

Challenging assumptions and accepted norms and analysing their impact. This includes (i) understanding the world as a complex system, in which entities have intrinsic value (ii) questioning ideas of past-present-future and the associated discourses (e.g. ideas of progress and continual growth), and (iii) opening up questions about what participants want and why (affect and desire).

(b) Embracing multiple perspectives

Engaging with diverse voices and contexts to develop more nuanced understandings. This includes (i) a move away from dualistic thinking and binaries such as us/them, human/animal, natural/human-made, and appreciation for the many co-existing worlds and (ii) broadening the past-present-future, making space for histori(es), present(s) and future(s) around any situation/phenomena.

(c) Investigating power and agency

Critically examining power relations and socio-political inequalities from an intersectional perspective. This includes (i) the biases underpinning worldviews (e.g. anthropocentrism, eurocentrism, colonialism) and networks of discrimination and privilege (ii) identifying hierarchies, as well as the dependencies and possibilities of action embedded in power relations, and, (iii) questioning and historicising narratives to rethink the present.

When youth engage in Deconstructing, they may focus on any of the three aspects—not necessarily all of them—as long as they begin to critically question underlying assumptions or power relations, which signals that they are ready to move on to the next dimension (Activating Change).

3.4 Activating change

The fourth dimension involves employing critical literacies to confront eco, social, political, and educational inequalities, imagining alternative futures, and identifying potential pathways to change through critical practices and speculative design. Students work towards desirable/preferable futures through experimentation using diverse transformative tools, e.g. creative interventions or political activism. The emphasis may be on small-scale changes which have a meaningful impact on young people's lives. Activating Change is crucial to the development of critical literacies in students and to the implementation of the Critical ChangeLab Model.

3.5 Processes of becoming

The transversal dimension requires students to engage in meta-reflection. This includes reflecting on how participants' perspectives, roles, and sense of agency evolve throughout the Lab, as well as how their ways of engaging with others and with democratic issues change over time. Such meta-reflection supports learners in recognising learning as a transformative process and in carrying critical literacies beyond the immediate Critical ChangeLab context. Fostering a culture of continual self-examination regarding the methodologies of learning rather than merely the subject matter empowers students to continue their learning journey.

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Figure 1. The Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework, detailed. This visualisation provides descriptive detail for each dimension within the framework and will be useful for educators planning and implementing a Critical ChangeLab.

4 Competency Framework

The Critical ChangeLab Competency Framework is conceptually anchored in the Council of Europe's *Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture* (RFCDC, 2018), and it advances the RFCDC's central mission of enabling individuals to participate meaningfully, confidently, and responsibly in democratic life. In line with the RFCDC, the Critical ChangeLab framework reinforces democratic empowerment by:

- **Promoting youth autonomy and agency**, nurturing young people's capacity to make informed decisions and take purposeful action in their communities
- **Fostering active participation**, creating opportunities for learners to collaboratively engage in democratic processes and public life
- **Strengthening individuals' confidence to interact in democratic contexts**, helping them develop the knowledge, values, attitudes, and skills necessary for constructive dialogue, negotiation, and collective problem-solving
- **Supporting social inclusion**, by cultivating competences that help learners recognize and challenge discrimination, promote human dignity, and engage respectfully across differences
- **Encouraging lifelong learning**, particularly through education for democracy that unfolds across formal, non-formal, and informal learning environments

Building upon this foundation, the Critical ChangeLab Competency Framework extends and deepens the RFCDC by articulating four interconnected dimensions that are essential for fostering democratic cultures capable of responding to contemporary societal challenges. These competences align with the RFCDC's four areas—values, attitudes, skills, and knowledge/critical understanding—while offering a more practice-oriented lens for democratic innovation, civic imagination, and transformative action. The four dimensions highlighted in the Critical ChangeLab Competency Framework are:

- **Critical Understanding of the World:** This competence expands the RFCDC's focus on *knowledge and critical understanding* by encouraging learners to interpret global, social, ecological, technological, and political dynamics through multiple perspectives. It foregrounds analysis of structural inequalities, power relations, and societal transformations, equipping learners to critically evaluate information environments and navigate complex, rapidly changing contexts. Figure 2 provides an overview of the competences that form the *Critical understanding of the world* dimension.
- **Creative and Imaginative Capacity:** While the RFCDC highlights creativity as one transversal skill, the Critical ChangeLab framework places imagination at the centre of democratic competence. It emphasizes the ability to envision alternative futures, generate novel solutions to shared problems, and use creativity as a tool for civic engagement and democratic renewal. This competence supports learners in reimagining democratic practices and imagining more just, inclusive societal arrangements. See Figure 2 for an overview of the competences included under *Creative and imaginative capacity*.
- **Transformative Agency:** Closely connected to the RFCDC's emphasis on *autonomous learning, cooperation, and action*, transformative agency refers to the capacity not only to participate in existing democratic processes but also to initiate and drive change within them. It empowers learners to identify leverage points, engage collectively, challenge injustices, and co-create new democratic spaces and practices. This competence underscores action-oriented learning and youth-led change. For an overview of the competences associated with *Transformative agency*, see Figure 2.
- **Democratic Disposition:** Extending the RFCDC's foundation in *democratic values and attitudes*—such as openness, respect, responsibility, self-efficacy, and commitment to human rights—this competence represents an embodied orientation toward living democratically. It includes cultivating trust, empathy, dialogue, reciprocity, and a sense of belonging to a diverse community. Democratic disposition frames democracy not only as a system of institutions but as a relational and cultural practice. Figure 2 illustrates the competences that make up the *Democratic disposition*.

Together, these dimensions articulate how the Critical ChangeLab Model operationalizes and expands the RFCDC by integrating critical inquiry, creativity, collective action, and democratic ethos. They reflect an integrated understanding of democracy as a lived, evolving practice shaped by young people's capacity to imagine, question, collaborate, and transform the world around them.

The Critical ChangeLab Competency Framework serves as a guiding instrument to co-design Critical ChangeLabs with diverse stakeholders (such as educators and young people), to steer collective reflection, and to assess the Lab's process (see D3.1 *Critical ChangeLab Process and Recommendations for Practice*). The competences are developed progressively across the Critical ChangeLab pedagogical process (see section 5), rather than being addressed in isolation or as discrete learning outcomes. Each phase of the pedagogical process foregrounds particular competences while simultaneously reinforcing others, allowing learners to build and deepen their democratic capacities over time. For example, early phases emphasise critical understanding of the world through questioning and analysis, while later phases increasingly engage creative and imaginative capacity and transformative agency through envisioning and action-oriented practices.

This progressive development reflects the model's understanding of democratic learning as cumulative and relational, where competences emerge through sustained participation, dialogue, and reflection. By aligning competences with the pedagogical process, the Model supports educators in designing learning experiences that scaffold growth, recognise interdependencies between competences, and enable learners to integrate knowledge, skills, and dispositions in meaningful democratic practice.

<p>Critical understanding of the world</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conflict Recognition ▪ Critical Assessment ▪ Historical Analysis ▪ Systems Thinking ▪ Critical Power Analysis ▪ Research Question Formulation ▪ Research Approaches ▪ Participatory Research Methods ▪ Participatory Research Methods 	<p>Creative and imaginative capacity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Creative and Critical Inquiry ▪ Futures Imagination ▪ Challenging Existing Paradigms ▪ Creative Inquiry of Social Issues ▪ Creative approaches for Inclusive Engagement ▪ Creative Facilitation for Collective Decision Making ▪ Challenging Norms Through Creative Approaches ▪ Creative Facilitation for Community Engagement ▪ Creative Facilitation for Local Transformation
<p>Transformative agency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Change Pathway Identification ▪ Resources and Method Selection ▪ Action Initiation ▪ Collaborative Networking 	<p>Democratic disposition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Democratic Reflection ▪ Democratic Attitude ▪ Democratic Awareness ▪ Democratic Advocacy ▪ Bias Identification ▪ Perspective-Taking ▪ Marginalized Voices Inclusion ▪ Adaptive Perspective

Figure 2. Overview of competences included in Critical ChangeLab Competency Framework

4.1 Critical understanding of the world

This dimension entails critically analysing and investigating eco-social issues by identifying tensions, conflicts, and historical influences. It emphasizes recognizing interconnected

challenges, questioning power structures, and addressing inequalities. Furthermore, it involves formulating research questions, understanding diverse research methodologies, and applying participatory tools to foster meaningful change. These competences are developed through age-appropriate and participatory research activities grounded in participants' local realities, enabling young people to investigate issues that directly affect their everyday lives. By engaging in methods such as community mapping, photovoice, or collective inquiry, participants learn to connect personal experiences with broader social, historical, and political contexts.

Competences

- **Conflict Recognition:** Ability to identify conflicts and contradictions in everyday life
- **Critical Assessment:** Ability to critically assess the implications of defined phenomena on their everyday experiences and those of their community.
- **Historical Analysis:** Ability to investigate and understand the historical trajectories that have shaped current situations and issues, linking past events to present conditions.
- **Systems Thinking:** Capability to recognise and analyse the complex network of interrelated conflicts and contradictions, understanding the interconnected nature of eco-social phenomena.
- **Critical Power Analysis:** Ability to identify and critically understand and challenge power relations and sources of inequalities within specific phenomena.
- **Research Question Formulation:** Ability to identify, articulate, and formulate research questions that are relevant and responsive to community needs and interests.
- **Research Approaches:** Understanding of various research approaches and methods, demonstrating the ability to select appropriate strategies for investigating and understanding specific topics
- **Participatory Research Methods:** Proficiency in applying and experimenting with participatory research tools, such as community mapping, photovoice, and

participatory workshops, etc. to actively engage communities in the research process.

4.2 Creative and imaginative capacity

This dimension focuses on envisioning alternatives beyond existing paradigms by questioning assumptions, exploring unconventional possibilities, and engaging with the creative and political potential of “What if?” scenarios. It cultivates the ability to imagine futures that transcend current limitations and encourages the use of artistic and creative resources to expose tensions, highlight issues, and enhance participation in deliberative processes. By questioning established ways of thinking and encouraging fresh ideas, it helps create space for meaningful change. It also supports individuals and communities in imagining alternatives together and expressing diverse viewpoints, thereby strengthening democratic engagement and more inclusive decision-making.

Competences

- **Creative and Critical Inquiry:** Ability to explore the political and creative potential of “What if?” questions, using them as tools to imagine alternative scenarios.
- **Futures Imagination:** Skill in imagining possible worlds and futures beyond current constraints, demonstrating the ability to think creatively about alternatives to the present.
- **Challenging Existing Paradigms:** Proficiency in questioning assumptions and accepted norms and thinking about unestablished and unconventional possibilities, fostering critical thinking, innovation, and the ability to disrupt conventional perspectives
- **Creative Inquiry of Social Issues:** Ability to use creative and artistic resources to investigate, highlight, and make visible tensions, issues, and contradictions in various contexts.
- **Creative approaches for Inclusive Engagement:** Skill in employing creative and artistic approaches to make participation and deliberative processes more accessible, inclusive, and engaging for diverse groups.

- **Creative Facilitation for Collective Decision Making:** Capacity to utilise creative methods to facilitate collective decision-making and foster collaboration
- **Challenging Norms Through Creative Approaches:** Capacity in using artistic and creative resources to challenge existing thinking habits and generate novel ideas
- **Creative Facilitation for Community Engagement:** Ability to use creative and artistic practices to facilitate socially engaged initiatives, encouraging community involvement and dialogue.
- **Creative Facilitation for Local Transformation:** Ability to apply creative and artistic resources to support and drive transformative processes within local contexts.

4.3 Transformative agency

This competence emphasizes the ability to design and implement solutions that lead to real-life change. It involves identifying and articulating clear, justice-oriented pathways for transformation and planning concrete actions to achieve these goals. It includes selecting appropriate tools, methods, and resources for effective implementation, adopting a proactive approach, and taking practical steps. Moreover, it highlights the importance of building, fostering, and sustaining collaborations with key stakeholders to work toward shared objectives.

Transformative agency may involve modest yet meaningful actions that demonstrate participants' capacity to intervene in their own contexts, rather than requiring large-scale or institutional change. These actions can include initiating conversations, reshaping local practices, or experimenting with alternative ways of organising and relating, all of which contribute to the development of agency and democratic engagement.

Competences

- **Change Pathway Identification:** Ability to identify and articulate clear pathways and planning actions for bringing about justice-oriented change within various contexts
- **Resources and Method Selection:** Ability to identify and select the most appropriate tools, methods, and resources to effectively achieve proposed goals

- **Action Initiation:** Ability to have a proactive approach and take practical actions that drive meaningful change.
- **Collaborative Networking:** Capacity to identify, seek, foster, and maintain collaboration with other stakeholders to work towards shared goals and collective actions.

4.4 Democratic disposition

This dimension encompasses the attitudes and skills required to foster democratic practices and engage in political participation. It involves experiencing, reflecting on, and critically navigating the complexities of democracy while cultivating core democratic values. Key dimensions include recognizing and evaluating democratic principles in practice, advocating for their reinforcement, and implementing strategies to strengthen engagement. It also emphasizes openness to diverse perspectives, curiosity about different worldviews, and a commitment to listening to marginalized voices. Furthermore, it requires the ability to identify biases, adopt multiple viewpoints, and remain flexible in revising one's perspectives considering new insights.

Competences

- **Democratic Reflection:** Ability to experience, reflect on, and critically engage with the complexities of democratic practices, understanding the challenges involved.
- **Democratic Attitude:** Capacity to cultivate essential attitudes to democracy, such as collective decision making, active participation, mutual respect, inclusivity, and collaboration.
- **Democratic Awareness:** Proficiency in recognizing and assessing the presence or absence of democratic practices and values within various contexts.
- **Democratic Advocacy:** Ability to advocate and use practical strategies to promote and reinforce democratic practices in various contexts.
- **Bias Identification:** Skill in identifying and recognizing biases within various worldviews, including anthropocentrism, eurocentrism, colonialism, and other dominant perspectives.

- **Perspective-Taking:** Ability to understand, reflect on, appreciate and inhabit multiple, potentially contradictory perspectives and worldviews related to a topic, demonstrating an understanding of diverse viewpoints on a given topic.
- **Marginalized Voices Inclusion:** Commitment to actively seeking, listening to, and integrating voices that have been marginalized to build a more inclusive understanding of issues.
- **Adaptive Perspective:** Openness and flexibility to change one's perspectives and opinions based on new information, understanding, and dialogues with others, demonstrating a willingness to adapt and grow.

5 Pedagogical Process

The Critical ChangeLab pedagogical process adapts the learning actions from the expansive learning cycle and is organized into five phases: (i) Grounding, (ii) Co-constructing knowledge, (iii) Envisioning, (iv) Putting into practice, and (v) Reflecting together (see figure 3). Similar steps appear in other approaches, such as inquiry-based learning—which includes orientation, conceptualization, investigation, conclusion, and discussion (Pedaste et al., 2015)—and project-based learning, which involves defining the problem, identifying knowledge gaps, gathering information, self-study, and reporting (Wijnia et al., 2024). All these approaches share a common principle: learning is driven by the learner’s motivation and agency. This active role helps learners connect deeply with the content, which is also a central idea behind the Critical ChangeLab process.

While the Critical ChangeLab process includes a sequence of phases, it is not strictly linear. The steps can overlap or be revisited as needed. However, it is essential to begin with the “Grounding” phase to ensure clarity and shared understanding of the process, and to conclude with the “Reflecting together” phase as a closing ritual to review and learn from the overall experience. Also, transitions between phases should be guided by participants’ readiness, evidenced through collective understanding, emerging questions, and agreement on next steps, rather than by predetermined timelines.

The Critical ChangeLab pedagogical process requires understanding democracy as an ongoing process that requires time and commitment. From this view, designing experiences that allow participants to truly live democratic practices requires planning sessions that are long enough for meaningful collaboration and ensuring engagement over sustained periods, giving trust-building, experimentation, and reflection the time they need. Such extended engagement deepens participation, supports iterative learning, and creates the conditions for participants to genuinely experience and practice democratic relations.

In Critical ChangeLabs, facilitation centers on fostering active participation and collaboration among all stakeholders. Facilitators play a key role in making the process transparent and accessible while ensuring that interactions remain non-hierarchical. This

involves using inclusive strategies that promote shared understanding, encourage dialogue, and support equitable involvement throughout the learning experience⁵.

Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy

Figure 3. Overview of the pedagogical process of the Critical ChangeLab Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy

⁵ For a detailed description of recommended methods and facilitation strategies, see the Critical ChangeLab output Democracy in the Making: Creative Methods for Youth & Educators. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

5.1 Grounding

This phase is designed to establish a collaborative foundation for inquiry. It introduces participants to the Critical ChangeLabs and their context—focusing on democratic relations and everyday democratic practices—while also addressing practical aspects of the process. The phase helps everyone feel grounded and connected from the start by building trust, setting expectations, and creating a shared sense of purpose before moving into deeper inquiry. A key objective is to co-create a safe and inclusive space where participants feel comfortable engaging and asking questions, cultivating their democratic disposition. Table 2 summarizes the main elements of the Grounding phase.

This phase consists of two main building blocks:

- **Introduce:** Participants are invited to become familiar with who is present and the purpose of the process. Space is provided for sharing motivations, interests, and expectations. Facilitators clarify their own goals to ensure transparency and foster an open exchange rather than a top-down approach.
- **Co-create a safe space:** The group collaboratively defines what makes the environment welcoming, respectful, and safe. This involves open discussion, agreement on shared values, and clear guidelines for handling challenges. By establishing these principles together, the phase sets a supportive and inclusive tone for the work ahead.

Table 2. Summary of P0: Grounding

Phase	Focus	Objectives	Dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework stressed	Key Competency Framework Dimensions addressed
Grounding	Establish a collaborative foundation for inquiry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce the Critical ChangeLab aim and process. • Co-create a safe space 	Understanding	Democratic disposition

5.2 Co-constructing knowledge

This phase is designed to collectively define, question, and analyse the topic of the Lab. It focuses on identifying issues that create conflicts and contradictions in young people's everyday lives and fostering critical thinking. Participants co-define the Lab theme, ground the discussion in personal experiences, and explore multiple perspectives. The process involves developing a systemic understanding of the topic, analysing current democratic dynamics and their historical evolution, and deconstructing assumptions about democracy. Emphasis is placed on co-construction of knowledge, recognition of tensions within democratic systems, and questioning dominant norms. Key competences addressed in this stage are related to critical understanding of the world and democratic disposition. This phase also encourages engagement with diverse voices and contexts to critically examine power relations and socio-political inequalities. It is linked to the *Identifying* and *Deconstructing* dimensions of the Critical ChangeLab Critical Literacies Framework (see Table 3 for a summary of main elements linked to Co-constructing knowledge phase).

Key building blocks for co-constructing knowledge include:

- **Co-define the topic:** Collaboratively determine the focus of the Lab, ensuring that all perspectives are considered and participants share ownership of the theme.
- **Ground in personal experiences:** Connect the chosen topic to participants' lived realities. Personal experiences serve as a starting point for defining the theme and as a pedagogical resource for structuring sessions. These situated experiences help make abstract concepts tangible and foster shared understanding.
- **Explore multiple perspectives:** Broaden the discussion by introducing diverse viewpoints, data, or external inputs. This may involve guest speakers, field visits, or creative media to enrich the conversation beyond the immediate group.
- **Analyse power structures:** Examine the systemic factors shaping the topic, including root causes, power dynamics, and structural inequalities. This step links personal experiences to broader societal patterns, promoting critical awareness and agency.

Table 3. Summary of P1: Co-constructing knowledge

Phase	Focus	Objectives	Dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework stressed	Key Competency Framework Dimensions addressed
Co-constructing knowledge	Collectively defining, questioning, and analysing the topic.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-define the Lab theme • Ground on personal experiences • Explore multiple perspectives • Analyse power structures and how they shape society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying • Deconstructing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical understanding of the world • Democratic disposition

5.3 Envisioning

This phase focuses on collectively imagining alternative futures and developing competences to think beyond existing paradigms. Participants are encouraged to question assumptions, explore unconventional possibilities, and engage with the creative and political potential of “What if?” scenarios. The goal is to cultivate the capacity to envision futures that transcend current constraints, as the ability to imagine what does not yet exist is considered fundamental for activating transformative processes in the present (Moore and Milkoreit 2020).

The envisioning phase aligns with the “Disrupting the Commonplace” dimension of *Deconstructing* within the Critical Literacies Framework. Key competences fostered at this stage centre on participants’ creative imagination and their capacity for transformative action. This phase is centered on envisioning alternatives that foster critical reflection on current realities, challenge dominant discourses, and inspire actionable pathways toward more sustainable and justice-oriented futures (see Table 4 for a summary of main elements linked to Envisioning phase).

Key building blocks for envisioning include:

- **Connect past(s), present(s), and future(s):** Exploring issues that span multiple temporalities, highlighting that perspectives on the past, present, and future are diverse and often contested. This means looking beyond linear timelines to understand how memories, current choices, and imagined futures continuously shape and reshape one another.
- **Craft critical speculations:** creating imaginative yet analytical scenarios or ideas about possible futures, while questioning assumptions and power structures behind them. It's not just about predicting what might happen, but about using speculation as a tool for critique—to expose biases, challenge dominant narratives, and explore alternative possibilities.
- **Imagine alternatives:** ideating transformations that challenge dominant discourses and open pathways toward more equitable and sustainable societal arrangements. This block emphasizes that the future is not predetermined but actively shaped through present choices and actions, making imagination a critical tool for initiating change toward futures grounded in eco-social equity.

Table 4. Summary of P2: Envisioning

Phase	Focus	Objectives	Dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework stressed	Key Competency Framework Dimensions addressed
Envisioning	Imagining alternatives and futures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect past(s), present(s), and future(s). • Craft critical speculations. • Imagine alternatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deconstructing -Disrupting the commonplace • Activating change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative and imaginative capacity • Transformative agency

5.4 Putting into practice

This phase turns ideas into action. Participants begin testing, prototyping, and sharing interventions that bring their visions to life. The focus is on creating meaningful change in local contexts, drawing on the “activating change” dimension of the Critical Literacies Framework. Key competences fostered at this stage focus on participants’ creative and imaginative capacity, as well as their transformative agency.

It’s a co-creative process where people work together to design practical responses. These actions aim to improve young people’s everyday lives and show what alternatives can look like. The orientation toward change is understood broadly—from shifting how democratic issues in daily life are perceived and understood to taking concrete actions within youth’s own environments. The focus is on moving from reflection to action—planning, experimenting, and learning from what works and what doesn’t. The goal is to help young people build the confidence to try new approaches and turn their ideas into concrete steps for personal and collective change (see Table 5 for a summary of main elements linked to Putting into practice phase).

This phase also builds practical skills—identifying pathways for justice-oriented transformation, planning strategic actions, and choosing the right methods, tools, and resources. It requires a proactive mindset and collaboration with stakeholders to amplify impact.

Building blocks in this phase are:

- **Design and prototype:** This block centers on experimenting with ideas through small-scale interventions such as artworks, prototypes, or campaigns. It emphasizes learning by doing, where testing and iteration become tools for discovery and refinement.
- **Share and discuss:** Here, ideas move into public spaces through pitches, performances, or presentations. Sharing invites dialogue and feedback, turning individual efforts into collective learning and helping participants strengthen and adapt their proposals.

Table 5. Summary of P3: Putting into practice

Phase	Focus	Objectives	Dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework stressed	Key Competency Framework Dimensions addressed
Putting into practice	Prototyping and sharing interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and prototype ideas. • Share and discuss publicly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activating change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative and imaginative capacity • Transformative agency

5.5 Reflecting together

In the Critical ChangeLab Model, reflection is not an add-on at the end but a continuous practice woven throughout the process. It goes beyond noting what worked or didn't, helping make underlying tensions visible and inviting participants to engage with differences, uncertainties, and discomfort in constructive ways—an experience that deepens their democratic disposition. Reflection is collective and ongoing, helping participants notice growth, celebrate effort, and plan ahead (see Table 6 for a summary of main elements linked to Putting into practice phase).

Integrated into creative and collaborative work, reflection fosters awareness of the process, informed decision-making, and shared ownership. Facilitators can use feedback to adapt sessions, strengthening participants' agency. In the Critical Literacies Framework, the focus is on "Processes of Becoming"—reflecting on how young people learn rather than just what they learn.

Building blocks in this phase are:

- **Keep reviewing:** Reflection is embedded throughout the process, creating ongoing feedback loops where participants can surface what works, what feels unclear, and what might need adjustment.

- Assess learnings together:** The phase culminates in a collective reflection that brings insights together, identifies impacts, and explores ways to carry them forward. This process is visual, conversational, and collaborative, reinforcing shared understanding.
- Decide what's next:** Participants and facilitators co-create next steps, which may range from personal commitments to sharing ideas with peers or presenting proposals to decision-makers. In some cases, this extends into planning future sessions to keep the dialogue active.

Table 6. Summary of P4: Reflecting together

Phase	Focus	Objectives	Dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework stressed	Key Competency Framework Dimensions addressed
Reflecting together	Foster awareness of the process, informed decision-making, and shared ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep reviewing. Assess learnings together. Decide what's next. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processes of Becoming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Democratic disposition

6 Methodological Repertoire

The Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy draws on practices from (i) Arts and design, (ii) Futures, (iii) Dialogical learning, (iv) Participatory research and (v) Community engagement. In the labs, these traditions come together to support collaboration and open conversations about pressing societal challenges related to democracy (see Table 7 for an overview of methods used at Critical ChangeLabs⁶. Building on this foundation, method selection is then guided by the Lab's goals, participants' interests and capacities, available resources, and the specific dimensions of the Critical Literacies Framework being emphasised.

In Critical ChangeLabs, **arts and design practices**, inspired by the participatory tradition, serve as catalysts for exploring challenges to democracy. In this context, co-creation processes using art and design methods function as a living laboratory in which participants practice democracy through activities like shared decision-making. By using visual, narrative, performative, and maker-based methods, at the Labs participants engage with diverse ways of knowing and understanding the world in complex, holistic ways. This range of creative practices also enables forms of expression that go beyond traditional text or speech, making participation more accessible and inclusive. (Dewey, 1934; Eisner 2003; Gardner, 1983; Greene, 1995/2000). Within the Labs, this is essential for helping participants share experiences, perspectives, and critiques that might otherwise remain unheard. For these reasons, arts and design practices are considered a key component of the Critical ChangeLab methodological repertoire, given their potential to support young people's cognitive and expressive capabilities.

Through arts and design, participants are invited not only to imagine alternatives but also to question underlying assumptions, power structures, and dominant narratives—a core aspect of criticality. The power of the arts in making visible the stories, voices, and experiences of those marginalized by dominant structures, and thus contributing to social justice has been highlighted in research (Bell & Desai, 2011; Goessling 2020; Sonn & Baker 2016). Critical ChangeLabs builds on critical arts and design practices to create reflective

⁶ For a detailed description of the methods implemented at the Critical ChangeLabs conducted during 2024 and 2025 see Critical ChangeLab project deliverables: D2.1 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 2 and D2.2 Report: Critical ChangeLab cycle 3. The deliverables are available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

and dialogic spaces where diverse voices can emerge and collective sense-making can take place. These spaces encourage participants to interrogate societal norms, envision transformative futures, and develop agency in shaping democratic life.

As part of the methodological repertoire borrowing from arts and design, **visual methods** offer powerful means of expression that foster alternative ways of thinking and help make abstract concepts more accessible, concrete, and understandable. Artmaking practices based on the creation of visual images, especially images that picture concepts, have been framed as inquiry processes due to their role for creating new insights and transforming perceptions. (Marshall, 2007). For example, techniques such as visual mapping or diagramming can reveal connections between ideas, highlight underlying patterns, and support collaborative sense-making (see Table 7 for a selection of visual methods employed at the Labs).

At the Labs, visual language is closely integrated with **narration and storytelling**, as these approaches enable rich ways of expressing and communicating complex ideas. Research has long highlighted the importance of narrative practices in shaping identity and culture, with studies examining storytelling in education (Luke & Freebody, 1997) and in collective mobilization (Beeson & Miskelly, 2005; Freire, 1994; Haraway, 1991). Stories are understood not only as a means of making sense of the world but also as a powerful tool for driving change (Coulter et al., 2007; Roney, 1994). For this reason, storybuilding strategies across different media can help identify and express problems, dilemmas, and opportunities related to European democracy. Examples include creating podcasts and audiovisual pieces that convey specific worldviews, as well as visual narratives in the form of memes or zines (see Table 7 for a selection of narrative methods employed at the Labs).

Performative methods allow for embodied forms of expression in which young people have the opportunity to explore a particular issue taking into account feelings and emotions, as well as considering multiple perspectives. In critical performance pedagogy, performative activities have been connected to critical citizenship since they allow for making oppression visible, act and resist (Denzin 2003, 2009). Methods such as theatre of the oppressed (Boal, 1985), as well as role-playing techniques (Belova et al., 2015; Shapiro & Leopold, 2012; Spyropoulos et al., 2022) have shown powerful ways to engage youth and experience democracy (see Table 7 for a selection of performative methods employed at the Labs).

Design practices based on making encompass diverse activities—such as welding, robotics, building, cooking, sewing, and painting (Peppler & Bender, 2013)—and have grown in popularity with the rise of maker education. Research shows these practices foster exploration, tinkering, discovery, and collaborative understanding through tools and materials (Wardrip & Brahms, 2015). The Critical ChangeLab Model builds on this tradition by incorporating Do-It-Yourself (DIY), Do-It-With-Others (DIWO), rapid prototyping, and hacking (Hunsinger & Schrock, 2016; Maravilhas & Martins, 2017; Martin, 2015; Orton-Johnson, 2014). Criticality has also been embedded into making through approaches like critical making (Ratto, 2011) and critical design (Dunne, 2008; Dunne & Raby, 2013) (see Table 7 for a selection of maker-based methods employed at the Labs).

Imagination is central to critical arts and design practices (Greene 1995/2000; Yusoff and Gabrys 2011), as the ability to envision what does not yet exist is essential for initiating change (Miller, 2018). In response to growing societal complexity, **futures literacy** has gained prominence, with UNESCO advocating a capability-based approach. Futures thinking builds on this by linking past and present understandings to the anticipation and creation of alternative futures (Dator, 2019). It assumes that the future is not predetermined but actively constructed, making diversity, agency, and empowerment key principles. Within education, futures thinking is framed as a meta-literacy that integrates language, digital, and critical literacies (Vidergor, 2023). Drawing on these ideas, Critical ChangeLabs aim to help youth reimagine democracy and act toward preferable futures. To do so, methods from futures traditions such as the Futures Triangle (Inayatullah, 2013), scenario building (Candy & Dunagan, 2017), speculative design (Auger, 2013; Durall, 2021), design fiction (Hardy, 2018), and The Thing from the Future (Candy, 2018) might be employed (see Table 7 for a selection of futures methods employed at the Labs).

The ways young people build relationships—by connecting, listening, and working together—are central to how they experience democracy. These relational practices shape their sense of belonging and participation, making democratic life something lived through everyday interactions rather than abstract principles. Within this approach, **dialogic and participatory learning methods** play an important role. They turn these values into action by creating spaces where teachers and students build understanding together through open conversation and different viewpoints. Inspired by Bakhtin and Freire, dialogue is more than talk—it's a way to learn from each other and grow as a community (Bakhtin, 1981; Freire, 1970). Building on these ideas, dialogic methods—such as fishbowl discussions, walking

debates, or rows of opinion—can be used in Critical ChangeLabs to spark meaningful encounters. These activities invite youth to engage with different viewpoints and practice reflective, dialogical analysis in a collaborative setting (see Table 7 for a selection of dialogic methods employed at the Labs).

Beyond using dialogic practices to foster participation, Critical ChangeLabs also draw on **participatory research**, which empowers young people by involving them as active partners in shaping research questions, methods, and outcomes—transforming them from subjects into co-researchers (Cahill, 2007). By engaging youth in this way, Critical ChangeLabs put democratic values into action through dialogue, collaboration, and shared decision-making, strengthening their sense of agency and voice. Seminal work in Youth Participatory Action Research (YPAR) highlights how when young people conduct research on issues they care about and see real-world impact, they develop critical thinking, confidence, and a deeper connection to their communities (Cammarota & Fine, 2008; Cahill, 2007). In democracy education, participatory research thus becomes both a tool and a lived practice: it invites youth to meaningfully participate in knowledge creation and community action, reinforcing that their perspectives truly matter (see Table 7 for a selection of participatory research methods employed at the Labs).

Fostering relationships with local communities helps young people broaden their understanding of societal challenges and discover opportunities for action. Exposure to diverse perspectives and real-world contexts encourages critical thinking and empathy, both essential for democratic engagement (Biesta, 2011; Dewey, 1916). For this reason, Critical ChangeLabs view **opportunities to engage with local actors**—such as community organizations, decision-makers, and civic groups—as a vital component of their approach. These interactions allow youth to connect theory with practice, experience the complexity of social issues firsthand, and collaborate to tackle challenges that matter to their communities. In this way, engagement with external local stakeholders becomes a reciprocal learning process, where young people and community actors jointly exchange knowledge, perspectives, and responsibilities (see Table 7 for a selection of community engagement methods employed at the Labs).

Table 7. Overview of methods used at Critical ChangeLabs

Type of practice and methods	Selected examples
<p>Arts and Design</p> <p>Methods: visual, narrative, performative and maker-based (*categorization is based on emphasis)</p>	<p>Visual*</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collage: Artistic technique where different materials—such as photographs, paper, fabric, or digital elements—are combined and layered onto a single surface to create a unified composition about a particular issue. • Drawing and sketching: Production of images by hand, using lines and shapes to represent ideas, objects, or scenes. • Mapping: Graphic representation of aspects such as emotions, concepts or relations. <p>Narrative*</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Memes: Production of funny or relatable pictures, videos, or text that share an idea or joke people can easily understand and spread online. • Podcasts: Creation of an audio show that people can listen to online or download, usually released in episodes covering different topics or stories. • Zines: Elaboration of self-published booklets by participants. <p>Performative*</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image Theatre: Participants use their bodies to create still images that represent ideas, emotions, or situations, often as a way to explore and discuss them. • Role Play: Interactive exercises where participants act out characters or situations to practice skills, explore ideas, or address problems in a realistic way • Theatre of the Oppressed: Performative method in which participants act out a local issue engaging with the audience in testing and discussing different solutions

Design and maker-based*

- **Brainstorming and Rapid Ideation:** Fast idea generation activity to foster participants' creativity
- **3D Modelling:** Process of creating three-dimensional objects or scenes on a computer, allowing them to be viewed and explored from any angle.
- **Prototyping:** Building simple models or versions of a product or idea to test how they work before making the final version.

Futures

- **Design fiction:** Design practice to explore and criticise possible futures through provocative scenarios narrated through designed artifacts.
- **Futures Scenarios:** Generation of visions about futures through narration and storytelling.
- **Futures Triangle:** Method for mapping temporal competing factors on a specific issue: the pull of the future, the push of the present, and the weight of history
- **Futures Wheel:** visual brainstorming tool that maps out the possible direct and indirect consequences of a trend, event, or decision in a circular diagram to explore its ripple effects into the future.
- **Historical Analysis through Timelines:** Creation of temporal representations to explore the evolution of a given issue.
- **Speculative Design:** Design practice oriented the critical exploration of various futures about complex issues.

Relational pedagogy

Methods: dialogic and participatory

- **Fishbowl Discussion:** conversation format where a small group talks in an inner circle while others observe from an outer circle, and participants can rotate between listening and speaking roles.
- **Five Whys Analysis:** Small group discussions using the "5 Whys" method to explore root causes

	<p>of an issue and brainstorm potential solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured Discussions: guided conversation where participants follow clear rules, roles, or steps to ensure focused, balanced, and purposeful dialogue on a specific topic. • Walking Debate: Participants express their stance on a given issue by moving around the room
<p>Participatory Research</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective Ethnography: collaborative research method where a group jointly observes, documents, and interprets cultural or social practices to build shared understanding from multiple perspectives. • Community Mapping: participants create visual maps to identify local resources, challenges, and relationships within their environment. • Photovoice: observation-based visual method in which youth use photographs to document their experiences, perspectives, and concerns.
<p>Community engagement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts' Interventions: external specialists share knowledge, insights, or guidance to deepen understanding and enrich discussion on a specific topic. • Field Visits: experiential learning method where participants go to real-world settings to observe, interact, and connect theory with practice through direct experience. • Participation in Cultural Events: experiential method where participants engage with art and cultural activities to reflect, interpret, and connect creative expression with learning. • Sharing Opinions with External Stakeholders: Youth present their views to experts and politically influential stakeholders for open discussion and debate.

7 Assessment

The Critical ChangeLab Model approaches assessment as an integral part of a democratic and dialogic learning process rather than as a separate, summative event. It is deeply process-oriented, meaning that assessment unfolds throughout the learning cycle and focuses on how participants engage, collaborate, and reflect, rather than simply on final products or outcomes.

Within this approach, educators act as facilitators of reflection and dialogue, supporting learners in jointly defining criteria and continuously making sense of feedback. By taking on this facilitative role, educators create spaces for collective meaning-making and ensure that assessment remains grounded in the democratic and participatory principles of the Critical ChangeLab Model. When involving participants in evaluation, two dimensions become central: first, the process itself—the practices, relationships, and ways in which change emerges throughout the Lab—and second, the individual and collective competences that participants develop as they engage with the Critical ChangeLab experience.

In this model, assessment is participatory by design. Learners are not passive recipients of judgment; they actively contribute to defining criteria, offering feedback, and shaping the assessment process. This participatory stance reflects the democratic ethos of the ChangeLab, where dialogue and shared responsibility are central. Rather than emphasizing grades or rankings, the model prioritizes formative assessment, using feedback loops to support growth and learning as the project evolves.

A distinctive feature of the Critical ChangeLab approach is its grounding in Expansive Learning Theory, which positions reflection as a core mechanism for transformation (Engeström, 2015). Reflection is not confined to the end of the project but is embedded throughout the cycle, encouraging learners to continuously question assumptions, evaluate progress, and adapt strategies. Both individual and group reflection are essential, creating space for personal sense-making and collective meaning-making. This culminates in a

dedicated reflective moment at the end of the cycle, where participants synthesize insights and consider future directions⁷.

Peer feedback plays a vital role in this process. Because the Model builds on dialogic and participatory learning methods, feedback is framed as a collaborative exchange rather than a hierarchical judgment. Participants engage in constructive dialogue about each other's contributions, fostering mutual accountability and deepening key competencies for democracy education.

In sum, assessment in the Critical ChangeLab model is not about measuring performance from the outside; it is about co-creating assessment practices that empower learners, sustain dialogue, and nurture critical, democratic engagement.

⁷ For a detailed description of facilitation strategies for supporting joint reflection, see the Critical ChangeLab output Democracy in the Making: Creative Methods for Youth & Educators.

Available: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cclab/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

8 Conclusions

This deliverable, *D3.2 Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy: Developing 21st Century Skills for Democratic Participation*, introduces the revised version of the Critical ChangeLab Model for Democratic Pedagogy. It explains the model's theoretical foundations, its guiding approach, and the design process that shaped it. At the heart of the model are five interconnected elements: the Critical Literacies Framework, the Competency Framework, the Pedagogical Process, the Methodological Repertoire, and the Assessment component.

The Critical ChangeLab Model is not intended as a rigid or prescriptive structure. Instead, it offers a flexible and adaptable pedagogical process that can be applied in both formal and non-formal learning environments. Rather than presenting a normative blueprint, the model should be understood as an open and evolving process—one that is continuously co-created and co-designed within each Critical ChangeLab.

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